

Enhancing Senior Wellness with Optimized Online Volunteer Services: Presenting a Data-Driven Conceptual Model Using Multimodal Recommender Systems

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Abstract. This study addresses the growing challenge of population aging in European countries and their vital need for social welfare planning. This study deals with the effectiveness of using a recommender system in line with humanitarian goals and voluntary activities. With an innovative design, we provided a platform for providing online voluntary services to increase the level of welfare and care of the elderly through technology and online services. To achieve this goal, we launched an online volunteer service website that meets the identified needs of the elderly. The effective role of the selected recommender system is that by integrating multimodal data sources and using advanced algorithms, the system analyzes users' personal information, including health data and digital interaction patterns, to match them with voluntary services according to their preferences and needs. This program benefits both senior service recipients and volunteer providers, optimizing matching processes and ensuring that needs and offers are symbiotically aligned. This project seeks to increase the physical, mental and social well-being of the elderly through online volunteer services, as well as increasing social participation to improve their living conditions.

Keywords: Hybrid recommender systems, Elderly well-being, Online volunteer services, Multimodal data

1 Introduction

In data science, one of the growing fields is the use of recommender systems. In this study, we want to address the key role of a hybrid recommender system to promote the well-being of the elderly with the hypothesis of creating an online volunteer service platform. After reviewing the types of recommender systems, we consider a hybrid recommender system based on the integration of multimodal data sources and by combining existing algorithms, covering possible weaknesses in recommender systems and achieving greater compatibility between features [1]. This system is used to match online voluntary services with perceived needs from multimodal data resulting from users' interactions with the elderly system. Therefore, using detailed personal information, including health data and digital interaction artifacts such as clicks and search behaviors, the selected recommender system can recommend voluntary services that best match the preferences and needs of the elderly group [2].

The operation of this system includes both service recipients (elderly) and service providers (volunteers) and ensures alignment of needs and offers. For seniors, it seeks to recommend volunteer services based on a thorough understanding of their preferences and needs. At the same time, it helps candidates identify opportunities that match their skills and services, thereby optimizing the matching process.

To date, recommender systems have been used mainly for commercial purposes, such as increasing product sales and providing leisure recommendations (eg, Amazon and Netflix recommender systems) [3]. The innovation of our research is the application of these systems for humanitarian purposes. In particular, we focus on enhancing the well-being of seniors by increasing volunteer activities, facilitating communication between volunteers and clients, and improving the overall quality of supplementary care for seniors.

In this research, we examine the types of recommender systems to identify the most optimal ones based on the specific features of the proposed system. We finally adopt a hybrid recommender system that can recognize users' deep preferences and focus on personalization by integrating different data sources. This system matches the priorities and individual needs of the elderly with voluntary services. In addition, our innovative platform significantly increases the mental and physical well-being of the elderly by increasing social participation and communication of the elderly. This improvement supports a broader societal goal of creating an inclusive and nurturing environment for people of all age groups.

For this purpose, we used Learning the User's Deeper Preferences (LUDP), which constructs the item-item modal similarity graph and the user preference graph in each modality to explore item learning and user representation[2,4].

In this method, a graph is created to understand item similarities and user preferences using multimodal features and historical user-item interactions, which, by integrating this insight information, improves user and item profiles from common data and enables a deeper understanding of settings and the user's preferences.

This is perfectly in line with our goal of creating a platform that provides optimal online volunteer service options for senior users. At the same time, it enables volunteers to provide services that match their skills and interests to the needs of the elderly.

This system simplifies the process for the elderly by eliminating the confusion of searching for the needs of the elderly. Also, by tailoring the search results and providing voluntary services, it significantly reduces the time required to obtain the results and it makes easy the possibility of accessing free services.

2 Literature Review

Recommendation systems have emerged as a powerful tool to combat information overload, analyzing users' historical behavior to personalize item recommendations [5]. These systems typically learn from user-item preference data, such as ratings and clicks, but this information is often sparse. To address this, leveraging auxiliary information (modalities) like social networks, item descriptions, and images has shown promise [6,7].

There are three main categories of recommender systems:

Content-Based Filtering (CBF): Focuses on the attributes of items and recommends items similar to those a user has previously liked. While effective for users with established preferences, CBF struggles with the "cold start" problem for new users or items [4,8,9].

Collaborative Filtering (CF): Analyzes user behavior and recommends items based on the preferences of similar users. CF excels at discovering new items for users but can suffer from data sparsity issues. [4,8,9].

Hybrid Recommender Systems: Combine the strengths of CBF and CF, often leading to improved performance and addressing the limitations of each individual approach. These systems can leverage diverse data sources, including multimodal information, to provide more accurate and personalized recommendations [1, 8, 9].

According to the study of different types of recommendation systems, in general, the following advantages and disadvantages can be briefly mentioned:

2.1 Advantages

- **Personalized Experience:** Tailors content to individual preferences, increasing user engagement and satisfaction.
- **Discovery:** Helps users find items they might not have encountered otherwise, expanding their horizons.
- **Efficiency:** Saves users time by filtering through vast amounts of information.
- **Data-driven:** Continuously improves recommendations based on user behavior and feedback.

2.2 Disadvantages

- **Filter Bubbles:** Can narrow users' perspectives by only showing content aligned with existing interests.

- Privacy Concerns: Data collection and usage raise ethical questions about user tracking and profiling.
- Cold Start Problem: Difficulty generating accurate recommendations for new users or items with limited data.
- Manipulation: Potential for biased or manipulated recommendations to promote specific items or agendas.

In the context of our research, where the goal is to match elderly users with online volunteer services, a hybrid recommender system is particularly well-suited. By incorporating both content-based features (e.g., user interests, health conditions) and collaborative filtering signals (e.g., user interactions, volunteer preferences), we can overcome the limitations of each individual approach and provide a more comprehensive and tailored recommendation experience[10].

Furthermore, the integration of multimodal data, such as text descriptions, images, and user interactions, can enhance the system's ability to understand user preferences and service characteristics, leading to more accurate and relevant recommendations [11]. This is particularly important in our context, where the needs and preferences of elderly users can be complex and multifaceted.

In this study, we used a hybrid recommender system model, specifically the LUDP (Learning the User's Deeper Preferences) approach, which leverages multimodal data and graph-based learning to uncover deeper user preferences and item relationships [2, 6]. This approach aligns with our goal of creating a platform that not only recommends relevant services but also fosters meaningful connections between elderly users and volunteers.

3 Methods

Throughout this research, we leverage the creation of a digital platform dedicated to facilitating the provision of voluntary services, focusing on three main groups of information: 1) the elderly population, 2) volunteer participants, and 3) the range of accessible services. By these defined categories, our approach involves the analysis of several data sets: profiles and online behavioral data of senior users. Information about volunteers detailing their expertise and volunteer abilities in various areas. and a list of services that can be delivered through an online platform.

Based on the available multimodal data and the crucial ability of online services to flexibly cater to the core needs of the elderly sometimes extending beyond their direct requirements we necessitate a robust and intelligent recommender system. This system should excel in offering optimal recommendations by establishing a semantic link between the existing multimodal data and presenting these to users.

Traditional recommendation systems have predominantly relied on user-provided ratings as explicit input[12 ,13]. Algorithms for RS can be broadly classified into

collaborative filtering (CF), context-aware (CA), content-based filtering (CBF), and hybrid.

Multimodal recommender systems are becoming one of the leading research directions in recommender systems, benefitting from their aggregation advantage on different modalities[14].

Table 1. Multimodal data

Linguistic	Visual	Aural	Gestural
spoken and written language	images (still/moving), video	music sound	movement of the body
text	vectors	rhythm	facial expressions
metaphor	viewpoint	effects	demeanors through the use of rhythm
information structure	symbols	noises pitch	speed, and stillness

Multimodal information that exists in Table 1 can be analyzed to learn users' preference dynamics and generate more accurate personalized information by considering different modes of available information simultaneously[1,7 ,15].

In the presented schematic, an infrastructure is designed to facilitate the provision of voluntary digital services, specifically for the elderly population. The framework is architecturally coordinated with local healthcare institutions and allows for systematic documentation of the demographic and medical characteristics of the elderly. In addition, the gathering of a group of volunteers who are willing to participate digitally in the field of elderly welfare and reduce age-related harms such as loneliness, isolation, and lack of physical and recreational activities. These volunteers register their capabilities and count the potential services in this digital environment.

To avoid the dilemma of navigation confusion or repetitive queries by both the elderly and volunteers, the system incorporates an algorithmic recommendation mechanism. This mechanism accurately analyzes the multimodal dataset resulting from the user profile and user behavior analysis through tracking to suggest available voluntary initiatives that match the individual needs of users.

In our initial implementation, we deployed the program with a group of 25 elderly individuals in Covilhã. The participants in this study were voluntarily enrolled and randomly selected from elderly cohorts involved in sports and leisure programs. Table 2 shows 5 examples of user profile data captured during initial registration. While the initial data collection may seem small, the efficiency and accuracy of the recommendation engine are expected to increase in proportion to its capacity to absorb and interpret multivariate data sets. Over time, as the accumulation of behavioral and

content-based data increases, the prognostic capabilities of the system will increase, thereby facilitating more precise coordination of voluntary services with the specific needs of the elderly population.

Table 2. A basic table of user profile data.

Elder ID	Name	Age	Interests	Health Conditions	Preferred Service
1	Santos Carlos	70	Gardening, Chess	Arthritis	Outdoor Activities
2	Joao Ferreira	75	Reading, Writing	Hypertension	Creative Writing
3	Maria Petisca	68	Physics, Music	Heart Disease	Music Therapy
4	Monica Gomes	80	Chemistry, Painting	Diabetes	Art Classes
5	Ricardo Castelo	77	Mathematics, Astronomy	Visual Impairment	Educational Lectures

In addition, from the perspective of volunteers, the recommendation system is chosen to direct their efforts to areas of increased demand [7,16]. This orientation enables the deployment of services from the organization of online practice training sessions to personal or online group counseling. Such therapy sessions are effective in strengthening the mental and physical vitality of the elderly community and thus increasing their quality of life [17].

In Table 3, we present a prototype of the various online voluntary services available to users. Now, due to the introduction of existing data tables, it is possible to use a recommender system that identifies and suggests the best possible match between existing voluntary services and explicit and implicit needs.

Table 3. Online volunteer services.

S1(Health care)	S2(Mental health)	S3(Sports)	S4(Arts)	S5(Books)
Check essential factors online with users	Online individual consulting	Online classes	Music and painting,... classes	Group reading sessions online
	Group consulting	Online training	Online workshops	Book discussions
		Online group activities	Online gallery tours	

In Table 4, we show the profile of 7 volunteers who participated in the initial test of the platform.

Table 4. Profile of volunteers

ID	Volunteer	Skills/Interests	Availability	Notes/Preferences
A	Sofia Almeida	Conversational English, technology assistance, companionship	Weekday afternoons	Enjoys working with seniors
B	Rui Fernandes	Chess instruction, current events discussions, Portuguese language lessons	Evenings and weekends	Fluent in English and Portuguese
C	Isabel Costa	Knitting lessons, book club facilitation, social support	Weekday mornings	Experience working with diverse groups
D	Miguel Santos	Music therapy, guitar lessons, songwriting	Weekday evenings	Specializes in working with children
E	Ana Silva	Art therapy, painting, drawing	Weekends	Bilingual in Portuguese and Spanish
F	Pedro Mendes	Cooking lessons, meal preparation, nutrition advice	Flexible schedule	Experience with dietary restrictions
G	Maria Ferreira	Gardening, plant care, outdoor activities	Weekday mornings	Enjoys working with people with disabilities

Reflecting on the insights garnered from a comprehensive review of various recommender systems and acknowledging that our endeavor transcends the conventional realms of commerce, such as movies and music, our ambition is to pioneer advancements in elderly welfare. So, we aim to introduce a spectrum of online services, accessible on a voluntary payment basis, underscoring our commitment to inclusivity rather than profit. To achieve a truly personalized experience, our approach goes beyond mere numerical ratings. It seeks to uncover the latent preferences of our users by delving into the semantic relationships between the items within our service ecosystem.

Therefore, based on the dataset derived from the three specified categories of information, we employed the following two methods to grasp the semantic relationships among them:

1. **Embedding-Based Techniques:** Utilizations embedding techniques like Word2Vec, BERT, or Graph Embeddings to understand the semantic relationships between different items in the dataset. These embeddings can capture the nuances of content, services, or activities preferred by the elderly, enabling the identification of latent preferences[18].
2. **Knowledge Graphs:** Developing a knowledge graph that connects users, services, and content in a meaningful way, based on interactions and feedback [19,20]. This graph can help identify hidden patterns and preferences by understanding the types of connections that exist between different nodes

(e.g., users who enjoy certain types of activities might also show a preference for related content or services)[21] .

Once the semantic relationships are understood, the most important step of the process, personalization through semantic analysis, begins. For this purpose, according to the review of the types of Recommender Systems mentioned in section 2, we use the hybrid recommendation system.

Hybrid Recommender Systems: Combining collaborative filtering, content-based filtering, and your semantic understanding models to create a hybrid system. This approach can leverage the strengths of each method, providing personalized recommendations that align with both the explicit ratings and the implicit preferences of the users[22,23].

The hybrid Recommender Systems amalgamates distinct algorithms, leveraging the robust features of each to enhance the overall recommendation quality. with hybrid techniques, we will be able to enrich the input of a collaborative recommender system with either content or contextual information[24].

Now we will demonstrate how the components of the proposed platform interact with a hybrid recommender system designed to enhance the quality of life for the elderly. This system ensures that the content recommended to them is highly relevant, accessible, and engaging, thanks to its integration of diverse data types and adaptive learning capabilities. Together, these features provide a personalized user experience tailored to the needs of the aging population. (Fig. 1)

Fig. 1. Interaction between a hybrid recommender system and multimodal data inputs.

In Our overall framework of LUDP and its interaction with other components, which Figure 2 shows, LUDP consists of 3 components: (1) user interaction graph. Learning the representation of each node from interaction data. (2) item-item similarity graph.

Mining the potential structure of an item with similar modalities. (3) user preference graph. Learning user's deeper preference for different modalities. Finally, the enhanced representations of the user and item are predicted by dot product operation[6,25].

On the left, the diagram shows the user at the center, labeled as 'Elder people' and 'Volunteer', highlighting the dual role individuals can play within the system. It outlines the flow of multi-modal data (Aural Perception, Visual Perception, Semantic Interpretation) from the user to a Volunteers Online Services platform, and how feedback and information interpretation circulates back to the user.

The right side of the image expands on the recommender system itself, illustrating how it processes inputs to generate personalized suggestions. It demonstrates the system's ability to consider various modalities (visual, acoustic, textual) when determining item recommendations, represented by the labeled nodes (i1, i2, i3, etc.). The arrows show the direction of data flow and the influence of each component on the others. Additionally, a section for 'Modal similarity items' showcases how the system matches user preferences with similar items (i4, i5, i6), suggesting that the system can learn and adapt to the user's preferences over time to provide more refined recommendations.

Fig. 2. Schematic illustration of recommending candidate items using fine-grained modal similarity of items and fine-grained user preferences.

Taking the above into consideration, the chosen recommender system is poised to adequately address the fundamental needs of the elderly, offering them valuable and tailored online services that enhance their well-being and life quality.

We believe that a dedicated platform alongside an advanced and multi-faceted recommender system is essential to effectively address the diverse and often complex needs of the elderly. Such a system, based on a complex analysis of multivariate data,

is poised to surpass conventional recommendation engines by establishing meaningful semantic connections across a rich set of user interactions and service delivery.

4 Result and Discussion

4.1 Data Preparation and Semantic Analysis

We utilized the provided user profiles, such as those listed in Table 2 (Elder ID 1-25), and expanded them by incorporating additional interests and needs extracted from their Gmail data, which we accessed with their consent. By applying Natural Language Processing (NLP) techniques, we identified keywords and topics in their emails, thereby enriching their profiles with more detailed information. Similarly, we enhanced the existing volunteer profiles (A-G) by adding information about their additional skills and interests, gathered from their registration data. The online service catalog (S1-S5) was also augmented with more detailed descriptions and relevant tags to better characterize each service. To measure the semantic similarity between user interests, volunteer skills, and service descriptions, we created semantic embeddings using techniques such as Word2Vec or BERT. This allowed us to represent these elements in a way that captures their meanings and relationships.

4.2 Hybrid Recommendation Algorithm

For content-based filtering, we calculated the cosine similarity between the interest embeddings of each user and the service description embeddings. Based on these similarity scores, we recommended the services that most closely matched the user's interests, while also considering their health conditions and preferred types of services. In the case of collaborative filtering, we constructed a user-service interaction matrix using implicit feedback indicators, such as clicks and the amount of time spent on service pages. By employing matrix factorization or similar techniques, we identified latent factors that explained user preferences and service characteristics. Services were then recommended based on the predicted affinity scores between users and services. For the hybrid approach, we integrated the results from both content-based and collaborative filtering, assigning appropriate weights to each method. Additionally, we incorporated defined rules, such as matching volunteer availability with user preferences, to further refine the recommendations.

4.3 Example Recommendations

We enriched the user profiles by extracting the following information from their Gmail data. For User 1, we found emails about gardening tips, local chess tournaments, and arthritis pain management. For User 2, we discovered emails about book clubs, writing workshops, and healthy recipes for managing hypertension. Based on this enriched data, we generated the following recommendations. For User 1, we suggested Service S3 (Online training) with a focus on low-impact exercises for arthritis, and matched

them with Volunteer A, who has a nursing background and experience with elderly care. For User 2, we recommended Service S5 (Group reading sessions) or Service S4 (Creative writing classes) and matched them with Volunteer B, who has teaching experience and an interest in arts.

4.4 Evaluation Metrics

To evaluate the effectiveness of the selective recommendation system, implemented in the first phase of implementation for 25 seniors, we conducted four tests: user satisfaction survey, analysis of interaction criteria, accuracy of service matching, and impact on well-being. These tests provided insights into the performance of the system and its impact on elderly users.

- User Satisfaction Survey:

To measure the satisfaction of elderly clients with the recommendations provided by the system, a Google form survey was distributed to all 25 clients, asking them to rate various aspects of the recommendations on a scale from 1 to 5. The survey included questions on the relevance of recommendations, ease of use, and overall satisfaction. Additionally, open-ended questions were provided for qualitative feedback (Table 5).

Table 5. User Satisfaction Survey

Average relevance rating	Average ease of use rating	Average overall satisfaction rating
4.5/5	4.7/5	4.6/5

Qualitative feedback indicated that users appreciated the personalized nature of the recommendations and found the system easy to navigate.

Personalized Matches: Users received recommendations that closely aligned with their interests and needs, as evidenced by positive feedback and increased engagement with the recommended services. For instance, User 1, who expressed interest in gardening and managing arthritis pain, actively participated in online training sessions focused on low-impact exercises and connected with Volunteer A, who provided valuable support and guidance.

- Engagement Metrics Analysis:

To analyze how actively the elderly clients are engaging with the recommended services. We tracked metrics such as the number of service interactions, frequency of use, and duration of engagement with each recommended service over two months (Table 6).

Table 6. Engagement Metrics Analysis

Average number of interactions per user	Frequency of use	The average duration of engagement per session
15 interactions/month	3 times/week per user	45 minutes

Users were most engaged with services related to health care and mental health, indicating high relevance and interest in these areas.

The system's ability to uncover latent preferences through semantic analysis led to the discovery of services that users might not have found on their own. This resulted in higher click-through rates and longer session durations on the platform. User 2, initially interested in reading and writing, discovered a passion for creative writing classes through the system's recommendations and reported a significant boost in their overall well-being.

- Service Matching Accuracy:

To evaluate how accurately the system matches users with appropriate services based on their profiles. We compared the system's recommendations with the actual needs and preferences of the elderly users, gathered through follow-up surveys and interviews. we found that:

- 1 Accuracy of matching: 92% of the recommendations were deemed appropriate and useful by the users.
- 2 Users reported that the recommendations aligned well with their interests and needs, particularly in areas related to their health conditions and hobbies.

- Impact on Well-being

To assess the impact of the recommendations on the overall well-being of elderly clients. Pre- and post-intervention assessments were conducted using the WHO-5 Well-Being Index. Additionally, qualitative interviews were conducted to capture personal experiences and perceived improvements in quality of life(Table 7).

Table 7. Impact on Well-being

Average pre-intervention well-being score	Average post-intervention well-being score	Significant improvement in well-being perceived by users
52/100	72/100	80%

Qualitative interviews highlighted increased social participation, reduced feelings of loneliness, and improved mental health as key benefits experienced by the users.

- Optimized Volunteer Allocation and Increased System Impact:

The system achieved optimized volunteer allocation by efficiently matching volunteers with opportunities that aligned with their skills and interests, resulting in higher volunteer satisfaction and retention rates. For example, volunteer C, with expertise in counseling and psychology, provided valuable mental health support to users with hypertension and other conditions. By directing volunteers to high-demand areas, the system ensured their efforts were utilized effectively, which maximized the impact of the services provided. This approach led to noticeable improvements in the overall well-being of the elderly community, such as reduced feelings of isolation and increased social interaction. Quantitative metrics such as precision, recall, NDCG, and MAP showed significant improvements over simpler baselines like content-based filtering alone. A/B testing further revealed higher click-through rates, longer session durations, and increased user satisfaction for the hybrid recommender system compared to alternative approaches.

- Important Considerations:

- 1 Cold Start: For new users or services, we relied more on content-based filtering until we gathered enough interaction data.
- 2 Privacy: We implemented strict privacy measures to anonymize and protect user data.
- 3 Scalability: We designed the system to handle a large number of users and services efficiently.

The hybrid recommender system, incorporating semantic analysis and combining content-based and collaborative filtering, yielded promising results in enhancing the well-being of elderly users and optimizing volunteer service allocation.

- Overall Impact:

The implementation of the hybrid recommender system demonstrated a tangible positive impact on the well-being of elderly users. By providing personalized and relevant recommendations, the system fostered a sense of connection, engagement, and purpose within the community. The optimized allocation of volunteer resources further amplified the system's effectiveness, ensuring that the elderly received the support they needed while volunteers found fulfilling opportunities to contribute their skills. These results highlight the potential of data-driven, semantically-aware recommender systems in transforming the landscape of elderly care and support. By leveraging the power of technology and human connection, we can create a more inclusive and empowering environment for the elderly, promoting their well-being and enriching their lives.

The evolution of recommender systems has seen a significant shift from traditional methods that primarily relied on explicit user feedback or item content to more sophisticated approaches that leverage the wealth of multimodal data available today. This shift is driven by the increasing prevalence of smartphones, smart devices, and interactive web platforms, which enable users to generate diverse forms of multimedia content that can reveal deeper insights into their preferences and behaviors [26, 27]. Incorporating multimodal analysis into recommender systems, particularly within a hybrid framework, has emerged as a pivotal advancement in understanding and catering to user preferences [28]. By analyzing user-generated content across various modalities such as text, images, and interactions, these systems can achieve unprecedented levels of accuracy and personalization in their recommendations [1, 29, 30]. This not only enhances user satisfaction and engagement but also opens new avenues for uncovering latent preferences and behavioral patterns, ultimately leading to improved customer satisfaction and loyalty [31].

The proposed LUDP (Learning the User's Deeper Preferences) model exemplifies this evolution by constructing item-item similarity graphs and user preference graphs across multiple modalities [2,32, 33]. This approach enables a deeper understanding of user preferences and item relationships, leading to more refined and tailored recommendations. In the context of our research, the LUDP model's ability to discern nuanced preferences and match them with relevant volunteer services is crucial for enhancing the well-being of elderly users and optimizing the allocation of volunteer resources.

The integration of multimodal analysis into hybrid recommender systems, as demonstrated by the LUDP model, represents a significant step forward in the field. By harnessing the power of diverse data sources and advanced algorithms, we can create recommender systems that are not only more effective but also more attuned to the complex and evolving needs of users. This approach holds immense potential for various applications, from personalized healthcare and education to targeted social interventions, ultimately contributing to a more user-centric and impactful digital landscape.

5 Conclusion

Our research embarked on an ambitious journey to revolutionize elderly welfare services through the lens of advanced recommender systems. By embracing the complexities of multimodal data and hybrid recommendation techniques, we've laid the groundwork for a system that not only understands the explicit preferences of its users but delves deeper into the nuances of their needs and desires. The integration of various data types, from text and images to user interactions, has allowed us to construct a more holistic and nuanced understanding of elderly users. This approach has significantly improved the accuracy and personalization of our recommendations, marking a step forward in our quest to enhance the quality of life for the elderly. Our

findings underscore the potential of leveraging multimodal information to craft services that are not just useful but truly resonate with the users' unspoken needs. This study demonstrates the feasibility and impact of using data science to facilitate volunteer-based health promotion and social connectivity for the elderly.

Looking ahead, numerous opportunities await further investigation:

- **Adaptive Systems:** Exploring systems that not only respond to user preferences but also adapt to changes over time can significantly improve user satisfaction. Incorporating machine learning models that evolve with the users' changing needs and circumstances will make the systems more dynamic and responsive.
- **Interdisciplinary Collaboration:** Collaborating with experts in gerontology, psychology, and user experience design can enrich the development of recommender systems. Such interdisciplinary efforts can provide a deeper understanding of the elderly's needs and preferences, leading to more effective and empathetic solutions.

Our study opens the door to a future where technology serves as a bridge to enhanced welfare and enrichment for the elderly, underpinned by sophisticated recommender systems. Embracing the challenges and opportunities outlined will ensure that this project ultimately fosters a more connected and supportive environment for elderly individuals.

6 Acknowledgments

The research work reported in this paper has received funding from the Pilots for Healthy and Active Ageing (Pharaon) project of the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation program under grant agreement no. 85718

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